

- 5 — several spots or blotches 2-3 mm size covering 11-25% of the seed
- 7 — spots or blotches 3-4 mm size covering 25-50% of the seed, with a few chaffy seeds
- 9 — pink spots or blotches 5.0-7.0 mm covering 50-75% or more of the seed, glumes tending to be more chaffy

Reduction and percentage loss in weight were calculated, taking the 1,000-grain weight of 0 scale seeds as

Effect of *T. padwickii* infection on rice seed weight.

Grade	Cauvery			Mahsuri		
	Weight (g)	Reduction (g)	Loss (%)	Weight (g)	Reduction (g)	Loss (%)
0	27.80	Base	Base	29.50	Base	Base
1	26.30	1.50	5.4	27.95	1.55	5.2
3	25.65	2.15	7.7	27.35	2.15	7.3
5	24.44	3.36	12.1	25.86	3.64	12.4
7	22.50	5.30	19.1	21.21	8.29	28.1
9	19.58	6.22	22.4	18.87	10.63	36.0

the base. As the severity of infection increased, seed weight decreased (see table). Weight loss ranged from 5.03 to

36.02% and was more pronounced in Mahsuri. □

Phytoalexin inducer chemicals for control of blast (BI) in West Bengal

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B1 incited by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., endemic in the northeastern hill states of India is particularly serious under upland conditions. Phytoalexin inducers, found to be effective in treating seed against brown spot, were examined for their effectiveness in B1 control.

We tested 20 chemicals in upland field trials in randomized block design, in 1984 and 1985 summer seasons using Pusa 2-21 and in 1984-85 winter season using Ratna. Rice grains soaked for 24 h in dilute (mostly 10^{-4} M) aqueous solution of test chemicals or water were direct seeded into 1×0.45 -m plots or sown in seedbeds and transplanted into 1-m^2 plots and treated with 120 kg urea/ha or 50 kg superphosphate/ha. At Lembucherra, B1 symptoms were noticed at 47 d in 1984 and at 27 d in 1985. Assessment for computation of disease index on the basis of number of leaf lesions in a plant and relative size of leaf lesion was made at 8 d and 22 d after symptoms appeared, following the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Ten of the 20 chemicals tested in 2 trials at Lembucherra provided substantial protection, reducing

symptoms by 72-89% in one or both trials (Table 1). Seven others reduced symptoms by 60-68%. Treated plants had fewer lesions; all 10 treatments in 1984 reduced mean lesion size by 60-73%.

At Pandua, symptoms appeared after 88 d. Assessment 10 d later

recorded 85-89% control in 3 treatments and 60-71% control in another three (Table 2). Lesion expansion was inhibited; proportionately fewer lesions of large size and many more of small size could be seen.

Many of the phytoalexin inducer

Table 1. Effect of chemicals in wet seed treatment to control BI infection. Lembucherra, Tripura, India.^a

Chemical ^b	1984		1985		
	8 d	22 d	8 d	22 d	
	Mean disease index/plant	Disease score ^c	Mean lesion length ^d (cm)	Mean disease index/plant	Disease score ^c
Control (water)	14.6	8	1.12	22.4	9
Ferric chloride	3.4 (76.7)	4	0.36	4.8 (78.7)	2
Barium chloride	4.0 (72.6)	5	0.34	18.9 (15.4)	7
Cupric chloride				5.6 (75.0)	2
Cadmium chloride	4.0 (72.6)	4	0.38	9.0 (59.8)	3
Nickel nitrate	2.6 (81.4)	4	0.31	15.0 (32.8)	7
Lithium sulfate				8.7 (61.2)	3
Cysteine	1.8 (87.7)	3	0.28	8.7 (61.2)	3
Sodium selenite	1.6 (89.1)	4	0.29	14.0 (37.4)	5
Thioglycollic acid	5.8 (60.3)	5	0.29	13.1 (41.1)	5
Cycloheximide	1.6 (89.1)	3	0.32	6.2 (72.2)	2
P-chloromercuribenzoate	4.0 (72.6)	5	0.3		
Sodium malonate				5.7 (74.6)	2
Sodium iodoacetate				7.1 (68.1)	2
Sodium molybdate				7.6 (66.2)	2
Sodium fluoride				8.4 (62.3)	3
Sodium azide				9.5 (57.8)	3
DL - norvaline				7.7 (65.7)	3
DL - methionine				9.3 (58.5)	3
DL - phenylalanine				8.3 (62.8)	3
Indole acetic acid				10.1 (54.9)	5
LSD (P = 0.01)	0.8			2.2	

^aData are averages of observations from 30 plants. Values in parentheses indicate percentage reduction from control. ^bChemicals used mostly at 10^{-4} M, except the amino acids at 10^{-2} M, lithium sulfate and cysteine at 10^{-3} M, sodium selenite at 10^{-5} M, and cycloheximide at 10^{-6} M. ^cBy the *Standard Evaluation System for Rice* 0-9 scale. ^dMean of all lesions on 20 leaves, 2 each (3d and 4th position) from 10 plants.

chemicals tested can provide seed protection from BI over a fairly long period. That protection had little relationship to their direct fungitoxic effects. Although the protection varied from one experiment to another, cupric chloride, ferric chloride, cycloheximide, p-chloromercuribenzoate, and sodium malonate provided good control under different cropping conditions and in different seasons. The compounds seem to act by activating a host defense in susceptible varieties that helps to restrict the number of infections and to limit lesion size, thus preventing the heavy inoculum buildup essential for severe BI infection. □

Table 2. Effect of chemicals used for wet seed treatment on BI symptoms. Pandua, West Bengal, India.^a

Chemical ^b	Lesions/ tiller (no.)	Proportion of lesions of different size groups ^c				Mean disease index per tiller ^d
		L	M	S	VS	
Control (water)	30.8	57	10	10	23	20.5
Cupric chloride	4.8	36	17	15	32	2.2 (89.3)
Barium chloride	22.8	53	12	12	23	14.6 (28.8)
Mercuric chloride	17.5	53	19	8	20	11.5 (43.9)
Lithium sulfate	15.4	34	17	15	34	10.2 (50.3)
Cysteine	13.7	42	16	15	27	7.7 (62.4)
Thioglycollic acid	16.8	47	15	14	24	10.1 (50.7)
Sodium selenite	18.3	34	11	34	21	8.1 (60.5)
Sodium malonate	10.8	40	16	14	30	5.9 (71.1)
Cycloheximide	6.2	36	14	14	36	3.1 (84.9)
p-chloromercuribenzoate	5.3	32	13	10	45	2.8 (86.4)
LSD (P = 0.01)						7.7

^aData represent average of observations from 30 tillers (one each from 30 plants). ^bChemicals were used at 10⁻⁴ M, except lithium sulfate and cysteine at 10⁻³ M, sodium selenite at 10⁻⁵ M, and cycloheximide at 10⁻⁶ M. ^cLesion size: L = large, M = medium, S = small, VS = very small. ^dValues in parentheses indicate percentage reduction from control.

Effect of additional nitrogen on incidence of the kresek phase of bacterial blight (BB)

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BB severity increases with N level. But the effect of added N on initial BB stages is not known. We conducted a pot experiment to measure the effect

of N on kresek.

Highly susceptible AC360 seedlings were transplanted at 25 d into porcelain pots filled with 6 kg dry field soil, and grown initially with 60 kg N/ha. At tillering, when tillers started showing kresek symptoms, half the pots were supplied additional N at 120 kg/ha. Each treatment was replicated seven times.

At flowering, no significant difference in kresek incidence was found (see table). But at tillering, plants receiving additional N showed

high vigor and produced more kresek-free tillers. □

Incidence of kresek in plants supplied additional nitrogen. CRRI, India.

Treatment	Total tillers (no.)	Kresek tillers (no.)	Panicle- bearing tillers (no.)
60 kg N/ha (initial)	13.3	3.7	5.7
120 kg N/ha (additional)	25.6	3.4	15.3
CD 5%	1.9	ns ^a	2.7
1%	2.7		3.8

^aNot significant.

Blast (BI) outbreak in northeastern Haryana, India

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is the most important disease of scented rices in northeastern Haryana. In 1986 kharif, BI affected scented rices Pak, Basmati, T-3, and Basmati 370 grown on nearly 80,000 ha. Basmati occupying nearly 80% of the area was damaged most.

We surveyed 60 fields at the dough to maturity stage. Average neck BI incidence was 20-40% in Ambala, 30-70% in Karnal, and 30-80s in Kurukshetra. Incidence was highest under water stress and in late transplanted fields. □

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